

Oxomolybdenum(V) and Dioxomolybdenum(VI) Complexes of Schiff Bases derived from Isonicotinic Acid Hydrazide

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Several new oxoMo^V and dioxoMo^{VI} complexes of Schiff bases derived from isonicotinic acid hydrazide (INH) and salicylaldehyde (INHSAL), furan-2-aldehyde (INFAL), 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (INHNAL), 4-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (INHDB), 2-hydroxyacetophenone (INHAP) or *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde (INHPCB) have been prepared, having formulae MoOLCIX, MoO₂LY (L = INHSAL, X = H₂O, Y = CH₃OH), MoOLCl₂, MoOLClZ, MoO₂L (L = INHNAL, Z = NCS), MoOLCl₂X, MoOLClZX, MoO₂L(OH)Y (L = INHFAL), MoOLCl₂X, MoO₂L(OH)X (L = INHDAB), MoOLCl₂, MoO₂LY (L = INHHAP), MoO₂L(OH)₂ (L = INHPCB). The X-ray powder diffraction pattern of one of the complexes has also been examined.

The chemistry of molybdenum has aroused considerable interest in view of its biochemical importance¹. Molybdenum is an essential micronutrient for microorganisms, plants and animals^{2,3}. In redox enzymes, Mo cycles between oxidation states +4 to +6 and the chemistry of Mo^V and Mo^{VI} have assumed immense importance because of its presence in certain metalloenzymes and its capacity of effect nitrogen fixation^{4,5}. In view of the importance of oxoMo^V and dioxoMo^{VI} complexes, we have prepared a few new oxoMo^V and dioxoMo^{VI} complexes of multidentate Schiff bases derived from the biologically active molecule, isonicotinic acid hydrazide (isoniazid).

Results and Discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) are coloured, non-hygroscopic solids and stable in air. They are soluble in C₆H₅NO₂, CH₃NO₂ and DMF, sparingly soluble in CH₃CN, (CH₃)₂CO, CH₃OH and C₂H₅OH and insoluble in water. The molar conductance data show that the complexes are non electro-

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES*

Compd./ (Colour)	%Mo: Found/ (Calcd.)	Mol. cond. ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-2}$) in		
		C ₆ H ₅ NO ₂	CH ₃ CN	CH ₃ OH
[MoO(INHSAL)Cl.H ₂ O] (Green)	23.8 (23.7)	1.3	5.4	9.8
[MoO(INHNAL)Cl ₂] (Red)	20.2 (20.3)	1.0	5.5	11.5
[MoO(INHFAL)Cl ₂ .H ₂ O] (Brown)	23.2 (23.1)	2.8	4.4	10.3
[MoO(INHDAB)Cl ₂ .H ₂ O] (Red)	20.4 (20.5)	0.8	2.1	11.1
[MoO(INHHAP)Cl ₂] (Greenish brown)	22.5 (22.4)	1.0	18.4	16.4
[MoO(INHNAL)(NCS)Cl] (Black)	19.2 (19.3)	2.1	5.2	65.6
[MoO(INHFAL)(NCS)Cl.H ₂ O] (Black)	21.8 (21.9)	3.1	11.6	4.1
[MoO(INHDAB)(NCS)Cl.H ₂ O] (Black)	19.4 (19.5)	0.8	2.7	6.5
[MoO ₂ (INHSAL)CH ₃ OH] (Yellow)	24.1 (24.0)	0.6	2.4	5.0
[MoO ₂ (INHNAL)] (Orange)	23.1 (23.0)	0.8	2.7	5.9
[MoO ₂ (INHFAL)(OH)CH ₃ OH] (Yellow)	24.4 (24.5)	0.5	2.6	5.3
[MoO ₂ (INHDB)(OH).H ₂ O] (Red)	22.2 (22.3)	0.7	2.7	5.0
[MoO ₂ (INHHAP)CH ₃ OH] (Yellow)	23.1 (23.2)	0.2	5.9	6.7
[MoO ₂ (INHPCB)(OH) ₂] (Yellow)	22.7 (22.8)	0.2	6.0	6.1

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses.

lytes⁶. All the oxoMo^V complexes show magnetic moment values in the range 1.61–1.82 B.M. which correspond to the spin-only value (1.73 B.M.) expected for oxoMo^V com-

plexes showing the absence of any Mo–Mo interaction. All the dioxoMo^{VI} complexes are found to be diamagnetic as expected for a d^0 -system.

In the case of INHSAL complexes, the ir spectra suggest that the ligand acts as bivalent tridentate. The shift in the ligand $\nu_{C=N}$ band and the absence of $\nu_{C=O}$ and ν_{N-N} in the spectra of the complexes show the coordination through azomethine nitrogen, phenolic oxygen (deprotonated) and carbonyl oxygen (enol form) in both the complexes^{7,8}. In the complex [MoO(INHNAL)NCSCl], OH group of the ligand is retained while in the other two complexes of INHNAL, coordination occurs via deprotonated OH. Further, the ligand is coordinated to the metal ion through carbonyl oxygen and azomethine nitrogen in [MoO(INHNAL)Cl₂], while for the other two complexes of INHNAL, the enol form of the ligand reacts with the metal via deprotonation^{7,9}. Azomethine nitrogen is another donor site as evidenced from ir data.

Ir spectra show that enol form of the ligand INHFAL and INHDAB coordinates to the metal through deprotonated OH and azomethine nitrogen. This is inferred from the downward shift of $\nu_{C=N}$ and the absence of $\nu_{C=O}$ and ν_{N-H} vibrations in the spectra of the complexes^{7,10,11}. The presence of coordinated solvent molecule is also indicated in these complexes¹².

In the Mo^V complexes of INHHAP, the keto-form of the ligand coordinates through carbonyl oxygen, azomethine nitrogen as evidenced by the shift of $\nu_{C=O}$ and $\nu_{C=N}$ to lower frequencies^{13,14}. Deprotonated OH group also is involved in coordination. In the dioxo complexes, enol form of the ligand coordinates with deprotonation. For the ligand INHPCB, a medium intensity band observed at 3200 cm⁻¹ (N–H) remained as such in [MoO₂(INHPCB)(OH)₂]. The complex shows a band at 3420 cm⁻¹ due to coordinated OH groups. The $\nu_{C=O}$ ligand band at 1660 cm⁻¹ shifted to 1650 cm⁻¹. The $\nu_{C=N}$ observed at 1600 cm⁻¹ shifted downward to 1595 cm⁻¹. Thus, C=O and C=N participate in coordination.

A very strong band occurring at 920–940 cm⁻¹ in the present oxoMo^V complexes can be attributed to $\nu_{Mo=O}$ ^{1,15}. Two strong bands with a separation of 30–35 cm⁻¹ observed for the dioxoMo^{VI} complexes at 890–910 and 930–945 cm⁻¹ assignable to MoO₂²⁺, show the existence of *cis*-MoO₂ rather than a *trans*-MoO₂ moiety^{1,16,17}. The positions of ν_{C-N} , ν_{C-S} and δ_{NCS} show that the thiocyanate group is N-bonded¹⁸. Non-ligand bands located around 580 and 520 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ν_{Mo-N} and ν_{Mo-O} respectively⁷.

¹H nmr spectrum¹⁹ of INHDAB shows signals at δ 2.9 (6H, s, N(CH₃)₂), 8.31 (s, HC=N) and 6.75–8.88 (8H, m, ArH). A sharp singlet at δ 11.7 (N–H of =N–N= group)

indicates the existence of the ligand in the enol form at the time of recording the spectrum, even though keto-enol tautomerism is existing in the compound. (The sharp signal found as a singlet at δ 2.5 may be due to the water present in DMSO-d₆ sample used)¹⁹.

The electronic spectral bands of the present oxomolybdenum(V) complexes show similar absorption peaks²⁰. A moderately intense band observed in the region 27027–25000 cm⁻¹ is attributed to O(π) \rightarrow d(Mo). The band due to the transition ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$) is probably masked by the above bands. The complexes exhibit two more bands, a medium intensity band at 20833–19230 cm⁻¹ and a weak broad band, spread over the region 15 151–12 820 cm⁻¹, assigned to ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$) and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$ ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}, d_{yz}$) respectively (the unpaired electron is in the d_{xy} orbital). The spectral bands at 15151–12820 cm⁻¹ indicate octahedral environment for the complexes in agreement with Ballhausen-Gray scheme²¹.

The X-ray powder diffraction pattern of [MoO(INHNAL)Cl₂] was examined and indexed for orthorhombic system, using Hesse and Lipson's procedure²². The unit cell dimensions *a*, *b* and *c* calculated were 10.79, 13.03 and 15.42 Å respectively. The number of molecules per unit cell was found to be four.

The esr spectrum²³ of two complexes [MoO(INHNAL)Cl₂] and [MoO(INHDAB)Cl₂.H₂O] recorded in polycrystalline form at room temperature exhibited only a single line pattern. The esr parameters were calculated and found to be $g_{\parallel} = 2.0213$, $g_{\perp r} = 1.9483$ and $g_{av} = 1.9848$ for the former and $g_{\parallel} = 1.960$, $g_{\perp r} = 1.913$ and $g_{av} = 1.9365$ for the later. The g_{av} value indicates the complex to be monomeric with Mo in the pentavalent state.

The thermal decomposition behaviour of ten oxo and dioxo complexes containing the coordinated solvent molecule (X and Y) in static air was studied. The complexes decomposed in three well-defined stages, leaving a final residue approximating to MoO₃. The quantitative elimination of H₂O/CH₃OH from the complexes occurred in the range 150–195°. In the second stage (220–300°), the quantitative elimination of the ligand took place and at 320–450°, complete decomposition of the complex to MoO₃ occurred. Varying lower values for the final residue were obtained in the case of the INHSAL complexes and this kind of behaviour is reported by earlier workers⁷. Interestingly, for the two INHFAL complexes [MoO(INHFAL)Cl₂.H₂O] and [MoO₂(INHFAL)(OH)CH₃OH], the amount of residue obtained was found to be higher than that expected for the formation of MoO₃.

On the basis of the available evidences, distorted octahedral (distortion due to Mo=O bond) geometry is suggested for the complexes.

Experimental

MoCl₅ (Aldrich) and MoO₃ (Lobo Chemie) were used. The other chemicals were of A.R. grade (B.D.H., Koch-Light and Fluka). Schiff bases were prepared by mixing methanolic solutions of the aldehyde or ketone (0.02 mol) with isonicotinic acid hydrazide (0.02 mol) and refluxing the resulting solution for 1–2 h on a water-bath. The solid products obtained on concentrating the reaction mixture were washed with methanol and crystallised from methanol. The purity was tested by tlc, elemental analysis, m.p. and ir spectra. One of the ligands (INH DAB) was characterised by nmr spectral data also.

Oxomolybdenum(v) complexes : [MoO(INHSAL)Cl.H₂O], [MoO(INHNAL)Cl₂], [MoO(INHFAL)Cl₂.H₂O], [MoO(INHDAB)Cl₂.H₂O] and [MoO(INHHAP)Cl₂]. **General method :** A methanolic solution of MoCl₅ (2 mmol) was added in small quantities with stirring to a hot solution of the ligand (2 mmol) in methanol. The pH of the reaction mixture was adjusted to 6 with NaOAc/HOAc buffer and stirring continued for 10–15 min. The solid complex that separated was washed with aqueous methanol and dried over P₄O₁₀ under vacuum. For the preparation of MoO(INHNAL)Cl₂, instead of methanol, acetone was used as the medium.

[MoO(INHFAL)(NCS)Cl.H₂O], [MoO(INHDAB)(NCS)Cl.H₂O] and [MoO(INHNAL)(NCS)Cl]. **General method :** To MoCl₅ (2 mmol) dissolved in methanol, NH₄CNS (–0.5 g) was added and stirred well. The blood-red solution thus obtained was added in small quantities with stirring to a hot methanolic solution of the ligand (2 mmol). The pH of the solution was adjusted to 6 using NaOAc/HOAc buffer. The solid separated on concentration of the solution was washed with aqueous methanol and dried over P₄O₁₀ under vacuo.

Dioxomolybdenum(vi) complexes : [MoO₂(INHSAL)CH₃OH], [MoO₂(INHNAL)], [MoO₂(INHFAL)(OH)(CH₃OH)], [MoO₂(INHDAB)(OH)], [MoO₂(INHHAP)CH₃OH] and [MoO₂(INHPCB)(OH)₂]. **General method :** A hot methanolic solution (50 cm³) of the ligand (2 mmol) was added with stirring to a hot methanolic solution (100 cm³) of bis(acetylacetonato)-*cis*-dioxomolybdenum(vi), MoO₂(acac)₂ (2 mmol) at pH 6.0. The stirring was continued while heating (50–60°) for ~1 h and the precipitated complexes were washed with methanol and dried over P₄O₁₀ under reduced pressure.

Metal, chloride and sulphur were estimated by standard methods²⁴. C, H and N were found microanalytically. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (MeOH) on a Hitachi 220A spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Varian spectrometer (60 MHz) using TMS as reference and esr spectra on a Varian E-112 X-Q band instrument with

DPPH as reference under a scan range of 2000 G and 20 mW power. The conductance of the complexes in nitrobenzene, acetonitrile and methanol (*ca.* 10^{–3} M) was measured at 300 ± 2 K, using an Elico CM 82T conductivity bridge with a dip-type cell (ec-03), fitted with Pt-electrodes. Magnetic susceptibility (300 ± 2 K) was measured on a Gouy balance using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as the calibrant. Diamagnetic corrections were computed using Pascal's constants ($\chi_{\text{Dia}} = -14 \times 10^{-6}$ C.G.S. units, for Mo⁵⁺ and temperature independent paramagnetism (TIP) for Mo⁵⁺ = 60 × 10^{–6} C.G.S. units were also incorporated)²⁵. The X-ray powder diffraction pattern was obtained on a Philips XRD (PW 1712) model (34 kV–10 mA), employing CuK_α radiation, with a scan speed of 0.05°/s and $\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$.

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